

parameter	unit	category	subcategory	name	description
<i>S_{mc}</i> ($mr = 10\%$)	μm	Field	Functional	inverse areal material ratio of the scale-limited surface	height c at which a given areal material ratio (mr , or p in MountainsMap) is satisfied
<i>S_{mr}</i> ($c = 1\mu\text{m}$ under the highest peak)	%	Field	Functional	areal material ratio of the scale-limited surface	ratio of the area of the material at a specified height c to the evaluation area
<i>S_{xp}</i> ($p = 50\%$, $q = 97.5\%$)	μm	Field	Functional	peak extreme height	difference in height between the p and q material ratios
<i>S_a</i>	μm	Field	Height	arithmetical mean height of the scale limited surface	arithmetic mean of the absolute of the ordinate values within a definition area (A)
<i>S_{ku}</i>	<no unit>	Field	Height	kurtosis of the scale-limited surface	quotient of the mean quartic value of the ordinate values and the fourth power of S_q within a definition area (A)
<i>S_p</i>	μm	Field	Height	maximum peak height of the scale limited surface	largest peak height value within a definition area
<i>S_q</i>	μm	Field	Height	root mean square height of the scale-limited surface	root mean square value of the ordinate values within a definition area (A)
<i>S_{sk}</i>	<no unit>	Field	Height	skewness of the scale-limited surface	quotient of the mean cube value of the ordinate values and the cube of S_q within a definition area (A)
<i>S_v</i>	μm	Field	Height	maximum pit height of the scale limited surface	minus the smallest pit height value within a definition area
<i>S_z</i>	μm	Field	Height	maximum height of the scale-limited surface	sum of the maximum peak height value and the maximum pit height value within a definition area
<i>S_{dq}</i>	<no unit>	Field	Hybrid	root mean square gradient of the scale-limited surface	root mean square of the surface gradient within the definition area (A) of a scale-limited surface
<i>S_{dr}</i>	%	Field	Hybrid	developed interfacial area ratio of the scale-limited surface	ratio of the increment of the interfacial area of the scale-limited surface within the definition area (A) over the definition area
<i>S_{al}</i> ($s = 0.2$)	μm	Field	Spatial	autocorrelation length	horizontal distance of the $f_{ACF}(t_x, t_y)$ which has the fastest decay to a specified value s , with $0 \leq s < 1$

Std (Reference angle = 0°)	°	Field	Spatial	texture direction of the scale-limited surface	angle, with respect to a specified direction ϑ , of the absolute maximum value of the angular spectrum
Str ($s = 0.2$)	<no unit>	Field	Spatial	texture aspect ratio	ratio of the horizontal distance of the $f_{ACF}(t_x, t_y)$ which has the fastest decay to a specified value s to the horizontal distance of the $f_{ACF}(t_x, t_y)$ which has the slowest decay to s , with $0 \leq s < 1$
Vm ($p = 10\%$)	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	Field	Volume	material volume	volume of the material per unit area at a given material ratio calculated from the areal material ratio curve
Vmc ($p = 10\%$, $q = 80\%$)	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	Field	Volume	core material volume of the scale-limited surface	difference in material volume between the p and q material ratios
Vmp ($p = 10\%$)	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	Field	Volume	peak material volume of the scale-limited surface	material volume at p material ratio
Vv ($p = 10\%$)	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	Field	Volume	void volume	volume of the voids per unit area at a given material ratio calculated from the areal material ratio curve
Vvc ($p = 10\%$, $q = 80\%$)	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	Field	Volume	core void volume of the scale-limited surface	difference in void volume between p and q material ratios
Vvv ($p = 80\%$)	$\mu\text{m}^3/\mu\text{m}^2$	Field	Volume	dale void volume of the scale-limited surface	dale volume at p material ratio
Asfc	<no unit>	SSFA		Area-scale fractal complexity	The slope of the steepest part of the curve, fit to a log-log plot of relative area over the range of scales multiplied by -1000
epLsar	<no unit>	SSFA		Exact proportion Length-scale anisotropy of relief	Radial profiles are extracted from the centre of the surface, by default every 5°, and the value of relative-length is calculated at a scale of 1.8 μm
HAsfc	<no unit>	SSFA		Heterogeneity of Area-scale fractal complexity	Calculated in a scale-sensitive manner by splitting individual scanned areas into successively smaller subregions given equal numbers of rows and columns
NewEpLsar	<no unit>	SSFA		Exact proportion Length-scale anisotropy of relief	Radial profiles are extracted from the centre of the surface, by default every 5°, and the value of relative-length is calculated at a scale of 1.8 μm

<i>Smfc</i>	μm^2	SSFA		Scale of maximum complexity	The scale range over which <i>Asfc</i> is calculated (the steepest part of the relative area versus scale curve)
<i>Isotropy</i>	%	Texture direction		Isotropy	Identical to ISO 25178 <i>Str</i>
<i>Tr1R</i>	°	Texture direction		First direction	Only relevant if <i>Isotropy</i> \leq 30%. Identical to ISO 25178 <i>Std</i>
<i>Tr2R</i>	°	Texture direction		Second direction	Only relevant if <i>Isotropy</i> \leq 30%
<i>Tr3R</i>	°	Texture direction		Third direction	Only relevant if <i>Isotropy</i> \leq 30%
<i>madf</i>	μm	Furrow		Maximum depth of furrows	Furrows are micro-valleys. The furrow analysis identifies the areas where points are lower than the neighbouring points on a given surface
<i>metf</i>	μm	Furrow		Mean depth of furrows	Furrows are micro-valleys. The furrow analysis identifies the areas where points are lower than the neighbouring points on a given surface
<i>medf</i>	cm/cm^2	Furrow		Mean density of furrows	Furrows are micro-valleys. The furrow analysis identifies the areas where points are lower than the neighbouring points on a given surface